

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CUSTODIAL FORCE PERSONNEL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences of custodial force personnel in the custody of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) at the Northern Samar Provincial Jail in Bobon, Northern Samar. It aimed to describe both the positive and negative experiences of these personnel and how they address challenges encountered in performing their duties. Using a transcendental phenomenological research design, the study focused on ten (10) custodial force personnel with a minimum of three (3) years of experience, ensuring in-depth insight and expertise. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and personal observations conducted by the researcher, with an open-ended interview guide serving as the primary tool to facilitate meaningful conversations. Analysis of the data revealed nine (9) emergent themes: three (3) highlighting positive experiences, three (3) highlighting negative experiences, and three (3) addressing how challenges are managed. Positive experiences included Motivation and Job Satisfaction, Workplace Relationships and Communication, and Professional Development and Achievements. Negative experiences were identified as Constant Safety Risk and Stress, Frequent Conflict and Workplace Pressure, and Emotional Strain and Work Challenges. Meanwhile, strategies employed by custodial personnel to address these challenges included Professional Growth and Positive Workplace Culture, Disciplinary Measures and Conflict Resolution, and Skills Enhancement and Readiness. Overall, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the realities faced by custodial force personnel, highlighting both the rewards and difficulties of their work, as well as the practical approaches they use to navigate the complex environment of managing PDLs in a provincial jail setting.

Keywords: *Lived Experiences, Custodial Force, Positive Experiences, Negative Experiences, Problems Encountered, Persons Deprived of Liberty, Provincial Jail, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Correctional institutions play a vital role in upholding justice and maintaining peace and order in society. At the heart of these institutions are custodial force personnel, who are entrusted with the complex responsibility of ensuring safety, discipline, and rehabilitation among Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). Their work environment is often challenging, characterized by high stress, limited resources, overcrowded facilities, and diverse behavioral challenges from inmates, making their duties physically, mentally, and emotionally demanding (Ponce et al., 2023).

Despite the critical nature of their role, custodial force personnel often encounter systemic issues that hinder their effectiveness. These challenges include understaffing, inadequate training, outdated facilities, psychological stress, and limited access to modern correctional technologies (Alipayo, 2022). Such conditions not only affect the performance and well-being of personnel but also compromise the overall effectiveness of correctional institutions, particularly in provincial and sub-provincial jails.

Recognizing these challenges, legislation has sought to improve correctional operations and personnel welfare. Republic Act No. 10575 (2012) mandates a custodial personnel-to-inmate ratio of 1:7 and allows for adjustments in manpower based on inmate population growth, ensuring proper monitoring, control, rehabilitation, and safety of PDLs. Similarly, Senate Bill No. 2352, or the Jail Integration Act, aims to unify provincial and sub-provincial jails under the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP), standardizing staffing, training, and policies to address inconsistencies, manpower gaps, and operational inefficiencies (Barcelona, 2024). Existing personnel are guaranteed security of tenure and may be absorbed by BJMP, with separation benefits provided for those who opt out (Senate Bill No. 1100. 18th Congress 2019).

Organizational change is essential for achieving performance excellence in correctional facilities. Developing a quality-oriented culture within the organization fosters continuous improvement, professional growth, and effective institutional transformation (Evans, 2014). In line with this, initiatives such as the Custodial Intervention Seminar in Bulacan have been implemented to enhance the skills, confidence, and problem-solving capacity of custodial personnel, reducing work-related stress and improving overall job satisfaction (Province of Bulacan, 2023).

Custodial personnel face numerous occupational challenges, including high job demands, workplace stress, overcrowding, and ethical dilemmas in balancing security and humane treatment of inmates (Liebling et al., 2011; Crawley, 2004). They are also exposed to workplace violence, trauma, and unpredictable inmate behavior, which necessitates structured mental health support, reintegration programs, and safety

protocols (Smith, 2022; Duggins, 2023). Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensure the well-being and effectiveness of correctional staff.

The organizational environment and leadership within correctional institutions are critical factors affecting staff performance. Ethical challenges, low morale, lack of supervision, and unclear organizational roles contribute to stress, burnout, and misconduct (Stohr & Collins, 2009; Schaufeli & Peeters, 2000). Furthermore, organizational commitment and job stress significantly influence organizational citizenship behavior, highlighting the importance of effective leadership and supportive policies in maintaining staff motivation and performance (Lambert et al., 2008).

Filipino correctional facilities face persistent issues, including poor staffing, overcrowding, insufficient funding, and outdated infrastructure, all of which hinder effective inmate management (Alipayo, 2022; Ponce et al., 2023). To address these challenges, government intervention is required through facility modernization, personnel augmentation, ethical training, mental health support, and policy reforms. Such measures are essential not only for enhancing staff welfare and reducing burnout but also for ensuring the safety, security, and rehabilitation of PDLs.

Overall, the experiences shared by custodial force personnel highlight the indispensable role they play and the pressing need to address the conditions that shape their daily work. By exploring their challenges, insights, and support requirements, this study aims to contribute to reforms that strengthen correctional management and prioritize personnel welfare. Ensuring that custodial staff receive the resources, training, and institutional support they need is vital to fostering safer, more efficient, and more humane correctional facilities across the country.

Research Questions

This study delved into the work experiences of custodial force personnel in Northern Samar Provincial Jail, Bobon, Northern Samar. Specifically, this study answered the following;

- 1) What are the experiences of the informants in the performance of their duties?
- 2) How do the informants address the problems encountered in the performance of their duties?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a transcendental phenomenological qualitative research design to explore the positive and negative experiences of Custodial Force Personnel at Northern Samar Provincial Jail (NSPJ) and the strategies they use to address challenges in their duties. This approach was chosen to capture non-numerical data, allowing the researcher to understand the informants' perspectives, perceptions, and experiences in their own words. Transcendental phenomenology, developed by Edmund Husserl, emphasizes

setting aside preconceived notions to perceive phenomena without bias, revealing the true essence of experiences (Moustakas, 1994). By adopting this method, the study aimed to provide an authentic, in-depth, and contextually grounded understanding of the custodial personnel's lived experiences.

Research Environment

The locale of this study is the Northern Samar Provincial Jail, managed by the Northern Samar Provincial Capitol and located in Bobon, Northern Samar. The jail occupies one hectare and currently houses 268 Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), comprising 260 males and 8 females, below its maximum capacity of 500. The facility is equipped with amenities such as a basketball court, chapel, infirmary, and livelihood programs in partnership with TESDA, including hog raising and agricultural production. PDLs are also allowed to plant vegetables within the compound to promote self-sufficiency and skills development. The custodial staff consists of 78 personnel (71 males, 7 females) organized into three shifts of 26 personnel each, rotating posts every two hours to ensure continuous security. The jail features two main buildings for housing PDLs and administrative functions and implements a "trustee PDL" program, which allows well-behaved inmates to build small houses within the compound. Social engagement is promoted through visiting hours and annual Prison Awareness Month celebrations. NSPJ provides a secure environment for PDLs while upholding their rights, and custodial personnel ensure the safety, security, and well-being of inmates while assisting in court transfers, emergencies, and rehabilitation programs.

This study involved ten (10) custodial force personnel at NSPJ, selected based on a minimum of three years of service. Their responsibilities include maintaining security, supervising inmates, enforcing rules, conducting searches, responding to emergencies, assisting in rehabilitation, and maintaining accurate records. One-on-one interviews were conducted at convenient times for the informants, allowing for open discussion and the option to decline any question, ensuring ethical research practices. Their extensive experience provided valuable insights into the complexities of custodial duties.

The instrument used was an open-ended interview guide, divided into two parts: one exploring the positive and negative experiences of custodial personnel, and the other examining the strategies and coping mechanisms used to address challenges. The guide underwent validation by a panel of experts to ensure reliability and alignment with the study objectives. Interviews were recorded using a smartphone, with informed consent obtained from participants. Informal conversations and researcher observations complemented the interviews, contributing to the study's findings and recommendations.

Data collection involved in-depth interviews and personal observations. A transmittal letter was addressed to retired P/Col Berbarido E. Raquiza, acting Provincial Warden of NSPJ, and upon approval, interviews commenced with the ten selected custodial personnel. Open-ended questions allowed participants to freely share experiences and coping strategies. Ethical practices, including confidentiality and informed consent, were strictly observed, and recorded interviews were transcribed for analysis.

Data analysis utilized Braun and Clarke's (Mauire, 2017) Thematic Analysis, which involved segmenting, categorizing, summarizing, and reconstructing data to identify recurring themes. The six-step process began with familiarization through transcription, repeated reading, and noting initial ideas, followed by coding, theme development, and interpretation, ensuring an accurate and comprehensive understanding of the custodial personnel's lived experiences.

RESULTS

Based on the result and findings of this study, nine (9) emergent themes were identified, three (3) themes described the positive experiences and three (3) also for the negative experiences of the informants, The other remaining Three (3) emergent themes were formulated as to how Custodial force Personnel address the problems they encountered in the performance of their duties.

For the positive experiences of the informants, the following themes were formulated, namely: *Motivation and Job Satisfaction, Workplace Relationships and Communication, and Professional Development and Achievements*. In spite of the positive experiences of the informants, negative experiences were also determined, there were: *Constant Safety Risk and Stress, Frequent Conflict and Workplace Pressure, and Emotional Strain and Work Challenges*.

For the themes formulated as to how Custodial force Personnel address the problems encountered in the performance of their duties, these are the: *Professional Growth and Positive Workplace Culture, Disciplinary Measures and Conflict Resolution, and Skills Enhancement and Readiness*.

Implications

DISCUSSION

The researcher employed the transcendental phenomenological research approach to extract significant emergent themes by re-grouping clusters through formulated meaning. This method facilitated the simplification of themes into categories, providing a narrative that encapsulates the lived experiences of Custodial Force Personnel at the Northern Samar Provincial Jail in Bobon, Northern Samar. This phenomenological approach aimed to uncover the essence and inherent meanings within the participants' experiences, offering a deeper understanding of their perspectives and the challenges they face within their custodial roles.

This study is primarily anchored on Safety Culture Theory of Taylor (2010) which states that we must eliminate or reduce hazards and dangers in the organization or workplace to maintain and create safety culture. Creating a safety culture involves more than just following safety rules, it requires shared values, attitudes, and behaviors among all members of the organization that prioritize safety at all times.

The Social Control theory of Reason (1990) supports this study. This theory posits that strong social bonds increase conformity with social groups and decrease deviance. Social control theory assumes that people are motivated to and capable of committing crimes without special training. This theory hypothesizes that the stronger one's social bonds to family and religious, civic, and other groups, the less likely one is to commit crime. Hirschi (1969) argues that social bonds promote conformity with the community's shared values and norms.

The Team Performance Theory of Michael West (2024) also supports this study. This theory is all about creating an empowering and satisfying work environment. It involves a group of individuals who work together to achieve a shared goal established by an authority, a team or team members. With the help of different models such as frameworks, a team dynamic can be analyzed and improved.

The following themes were formulated exploring the lived experiences of the Custodial Force Personnel in custody of the Person Deprived of Liberty (PDL):

I. Experiences of the Informants in the Custody of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)

A. Positive Experiences of the Informants in the performance of their Duties

1. **Motivation and Job Satisfaction.** This themes involves understanding the factors that drive their commitment and contentment within their roles. Custodial Force Personnel often cite their families as a primary source of motivation. The responsibility of providing for their loved ones becomes a driving force, instilling a sense of purpose and dedication to their daily work.

Motivation and job satisfaction are important factors in driving employee commitment and productivity, particularly among custodial force personnel. Moreover, Team Performance Theory emphasize that motivation directly impacts job performance and organizational commitment. Additionally, empirical evidence demonstrates that motivated employees mean better organizational performance (Raschke, 2016).

Furthermore, they often cite their families as a primary source of motivation, supporting one's family is a major reason why many people work (Menges, 2017). In this regard, Social Control Theory further reinforces the importance of strong social bonds in fostering engagement and accountability. When combined, these factors highlight that when custodial personnel feel connected to their colleagues and the organization, they develop a stronger sense of responsibility, which enhances job satisfaction and performance.

2. **Workplace Relationships and Communication.** Positive relationships among Custodial Force Personnel are essential for creating a cohesive and supportive work environment. These relationships contribute to teamwork, effective collaboration, and a shared sense of responsibility. Clear and open communication channels are essential for ensuring that information flows efficiently within the custodial team.

Miscommunication or lack of information can lead to misunderstandings and negatively impact relationships.

Positive workplace relationships and good communication are important for building a united and effective custodial team. This supports the Social Control Theory, which says that strong social bonds help people stay accountable and follow rules. In correctional settings, teamwork is especially important to keep everyone safe and committed to their duties. Dulay (2022) also noted that having a positive attitude at work improves teamwork and cooperation among staff.

Ehrhardt (2014) explained that good workplace relationships help people reach both personal and professional goals. This fits with Team Performance Theory, which says teamwork and support lead to success. Campbell (2022) added that clear communication improves morale, productivity, and safety by helping staff share updates and respond to threats. Poor communication, on the other hand, can cause mistakes and safety issues. Overall, strong relationships and clear communication lead to a more motivated and efficient custodial team, creating a safer and better-managed facility. Improving these areas helps both the staff and the whole custodial system.

3. Professional Development and Achievements. Custodial Force Personnel often engage in continuous training programs and skill development activities. These initiatives are designed to enhance their capabilities, keep them updated on industry best practices, and improve their overall effectiveness in their roles

According to Santos (2016), personal development is the process by which individuals reflect on themselves, gain a deeper understanding of who they are, accept their strengths and weaknesses, and adopt new values, attitudes, behaviors, and thinking skills to reach their fullest potential. It was further explained that it involves striving to be the best version of oneself through continuous self-discovery, self-improvement, and self-realization. It is a lifelong journey toward personal growth and fulfillment (Santos, 2016).

Custodial Force Personnel engage in continuous training and skill development to enhance their technical skills, emotional intelligence, and overall effectiveness. Moreover, Social Control Theory highlights that strong social bonds foster accountability and reduce negative behaviors, which professional development helps cultivate within custodial teams and in their interactions with Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). Additionally, Team Performance Theory further reinforces that skill enhancement, communication, and collaboration are essential for maintaining security and order. Through this lens, training enables custodial personnel strengthen teamwork, boost morale, and improve workplace efficiency. Furthermore, employee training and development occurs at different levels of the organization and helps individuals in attaining diverse goals (Walters, 2017). Ultimately, integrating personal growth with Social Control Theory and Team Performance Theory enhances custodial personnel's effectiveness, strengthens professional relationships, and supports the rehabilitation process within correctional facilities.

B. Negative Experiences of the Informants in the Performance of their Duties

1. **Constant Safety Risk and Stress.** This themes provide an overview of the custodial setting and the inherent challenges associated with maintaining safety. It introduce the concept of vigilance and its critical role in addressing potential risks and threats. Emphasize the constant need for vigilance and its impact on the daily experiences of custodial personnel.

The Safety Culture Theory highlights the importance of training and behavior change to improve safety at work, rather than trying to change people's attitudes (Gilbert, 2018). For custodial personnel, skills training is essential for following security rules, assessing risks, and handling emergencies, helping them stay alert in high-risk situations.

Likewise, Social Control Theory explains that strong social bonds in structured environments promote discipline and reduce misconduct. In jails, professional training helps build these bonds by reinforcing proper behavior, ethics, and institutional values (Wickert, 2019).

Team Performance Theory also stresses that ongoing learning and skill development are key to building trust, teamwork, and effectiveness. As Workleap (2023) puts it, successful teams are built through careful planning and support. Since custodial staff work in team-based, high-pressure settings, training in communication, conflict resolution, and crisis response improves coordination and overall performance.

2. **Frequent Conflict and Workplace Pressure.** In complex custodial settings, where tensions often arise and interactions require a careful balance of authority and empathy, the themes of Conflict Management and Professional Attitude become especially important. This section explores how custodial force personnel handle conflicts within their environment while maintaining professionalism in their interactions with PDLs, ensuring order, respect, and humane treatment are upheld at all times.

Effective conflict management and professionalism are crucial in custodial settings, where personnel must navigate high-pressure interactions with PDLs, colleagues, and superiors. Moreover, maintaining control while fostering mutual respect requires strong communication skills, emotional intelligence, and adherence to ethical standards. The Safety Culture Theory emphasizes proactive conflict resolution strategies that prioritize safety and professionalism over reactive discipline. In this regard, actions for safety can be treated as a starting point for the operationalization of sustainable development, especially its social challenges (Kaczmarek, 2022).

Furthermore, Social Control Theory highlights how strong social bonds reduce misconduct, reinforcing the need for custodial personnel to build positive relationships that foster respect and compliance. Research indicates that coercive experiences within prison are associated with engagement in violent misconduct as well as defiant and institutionalized forms of inmate resistance. However, social support is not consistently

related to either misconduct or resistance. Additionally, results suggest that prison staff can inhibit these reactive behaviors by effectively reducing violence and promoting safety within prisons (Butler, 2014).

Likewise, Team Performance Theory underscores the importance of teamwork in managing workplace stress and ensuring coordinated responses to high-risk situations. By integrating these theoretical frameworks, custodial institutions can cultivate a structured approach to conflict resolution, enhance teamwork, and create a safer, more professional, and collaborative work environment. In order to improve work satisfaction, employee engagement, and overall organizational performance, useful advice will be made to assist organizations in implementing effective conflict management practices (Rusady, 2024).

3. Emotional Strain and Work Challenges. This theme shows the emotional and mental stress that custodial force personnel go through because of their tough job. Every day, they deal with challenges like handling inmate behavior, working long hours, and facing safety risks. These pressures can cause tiredness, stress, and emotional exhaustion. Over time, the job can lower their focus, energy, and well-being. This theme reveals the hidden burden they carry while working in a high-pressure environment.

Custodial Force Personnel experience high levels of emotional stress, financial problems, and challenges in balancing work and personal life. These issues affect their well-being and job performance. According to Safety Culture Theory, support systems like mental health programs and stress management are important in helping workers cope. Monteiro (2023) explains that a positive workplace culture with good leadership, clear job roles, and social support can improve mental health.

Social Control Theory also shows that strong bonds with family and co-workers help prevent stress-related problems. Sun (2023) adds that people with strong social connections are less likely to engage in harmful behavior, while weak social bonds may lead to misconduct.

Team Performance Theory highlights the importance of teamwork in reducing emotional stress. Research shows that strong teamwork and good well-being help prevent burnout in high-stress jobs. On the other hand, the lack of teamwork or support increases the risk of burnout (Saud & Rice, 2024). By using these ideas, custodial institutions can create programs that build resilience, boost motivation, and improve job satisfaction, leading to a healthier and more effective workforce.

II. Addressing the Problems Encountered in the Performance of their Duties

1. Professional Development and Workplace Culture. This themes zooms in on two fundamental aspects that significantly shape their experiences, the pursuit of professional development and the complexities of workplace culture.

A positive workplace is essential to the success of any organization. Both employees and leaders benefit from creating an environment that promotes growth, motivation, and mutual respect. Safety Culture Theory emphasizes that proactive safety practices and ongoing skill development help maintain a secure and effective custodial environment. Organizational culture functions much like personal identity it reflects core values and beliefs and shapes behavior. In workplaces with a strong safety culture, there is a shared commitment to making safety a top priority, which guides daily actions and decision-making (Bisbey et al., 2021).

Furthermore, Social Control Theory underscores the role of strong workplace bonds in promoting adherence to organizational norms and reducing misconduct. Reckless (2010), a prominent American criminologist and sociologist developed a similar theory, which explains how social norms, values and beliefs are used to regulate behavior and prevent deviance, according to him, social control can be either external or internal, and is necessary for maintaining social order and stability (Philonotes, 2023). Additionally, Team Performance Theory emphasizes collaboration, trust, and communication as essential for maintaining order and efficiency. Many organizations are intentionally fostering a collaborative team-based culture, and feeling like a part of a team is a primary driver of employee engagement (Johnson, 2021). Together, these theories illustrate how professional growth and a positive workplace culture enhance safety, teamwork, and overall custodial effectiveness.

2. Disciplinary Measures and Conflict Resolution. Within the controlled confines of custodial environments, the challenges encountered by Custodial Force Personnel in maintaining discipline and resolving conflicts stand as pillars defining the complexities of their roles.

The balance between discipline and respect is crucial in maintaining order and resolving conflicts within custodial environments. Moreover, Safety Culture Theory emphasizes structured disciplinary systems that prioritize proactive conflict prevention. Since conflict is an inevitable aspect of any workplace, stemming from diverse perspectives, goals, and personalities. However, the key to a successful and thriving workplace lies not in avoiding conflict but in managing and resolving it effectively (Barnes, 2024).

Furthermore, Social Control Theory highlights how strong social bonds and fair enforcement of rules foster compliance and reduce misconduct, is the process whereby society seeks to ensure conformity to the dominant values and norms in that society. It explains that social control is the process whereby society seeks to ensure conformity to the dominant values and norms. This process can be either informal, as in the exercise of control through customs, norms, and expectations, or formal, as in the exercise of control through laws or other official regulations (Perera, 2024).

Additionally, Team Performance Theory underscores teamwork and communication in ensuring consistent, unbiased conflict resolution. Research suggest that conflict resolution focuses on resolving the underlying problem rather than blaming individuals (Adham, 2023). While discipline establishes structure, respect enhances its

effectiveness, encouraging cooperation, reducing hostility, and fostering a culture of fairness and accountability. Eventually, a balanced approach to discipline and respect strengthens compliance, trust, and workplace harmony, leading to a more structured and effective custodial environment.

3. **Skills Enhancement and Readiness.** In the ever-evolving setting of custodial roles, the relentless pursuit of skills enhancement and unwavering adherence to security protocols stand as imperatives that define the effectiveness of Custodial Force Personnel. This theme embarks on an exploration of the challenges encountered by Custodial Force Personnel as they navigate the dynamic demands of skill development and the rigorous adherence to security protocols.

Skills enhancement and readiness in custodial roles are vital for maintaining security and efficiency. Moreover, many organizations prioritize custodial training to ensure that their custodial staff is skilled and knowledgeable in the latest techniques and technologies (Capital, 2024). The Safety Culture Theory emphasizes structured training to reinforce occupational safety and risk management. Research suggest that if there were no barriers, the development of a safety culture would never form a problem and safety cultures would abound (Hudson, 2001).

Furthermore, Social Control Theory highlights how training strengthens professional bonds, fostering adherence to institutional values and security protocols. It is commonly used to help us understand and reduce levels of criminal activity. It's based upon the idea that an individual's basic belief system, values, morals, commitments and relationships foster a lawful environment (Schubert, 2023).

Additionally, Team Performance Theory underscores the importance of technical and interpersonal skills in enhancing teamwork and operational coordination. Without continuous training, personnel may struggle to uphold security measures, putting themselves and inmates at risk. Investing in skill development ensures a competent, engaged, and cohesive workforce, reinforcing a culture of trust, cooperation, and safety.

Conclusions

This qualitative work concludes that custodial force personnel navigate a demanding yet meaningful profession shaped by both positive and challenging experiences. Through one-on-one interviews, the study revealed that despite stress, resource constraints, and interpersonal difficulties, personnel remain committed to their roles through teamwork, resilience, and adherence to institutional protocols. Their lived experiences highlight the importance of organizational support, strong communication, and continuous training in fostering a safer, more effective, and more humane custodial environment. The insights gathered from this study contribute valuable knowledge that can guide future policy development, institutional reforms, and capacity-building initiatives.

Recommendations

1. The Department of Justice is urged to strengthen correctional reforms by improving training programs, welfare services, and ethical standards grounded in human rights principles.
2. Local Government Units (LGUs) should utilize the study's findings to better understand correctional operations and allocate resources effectively, including facility enhancement and staff support.
3. Families of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) can use the insights from this study to gain a clearer understanding of the correctional environment, promoting empathy and informed advocacy.
4. Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) may develop greater appreciation for the challenges faced by custodial staff, fostering mutual respect and reducing conflict within facilities.
5. The community plays a vital role in recognizing the sacrifices and contributions of custodial personnel, supporting reintegration programs and justice-related initiatives.
6. The judicial sector is encouraged to integrate the study's findings into sentencing, rehabilitation, and correctional policies, ensuring decisions reflect humane and rehabilitative standards.
7. Future researchers may use this study as a foundation for further exploration of correctional issues, promoting interdisciplinary approaches that strengthen policy and practice.
8. An in-depth study on custodial personnel in Job Order (JO) status for more than three years is recommended to examine the effects of job insecurity on their work performance and personal well-being.
9. A study on recruitment standards for custodial personnel is encouraged, particularly assessing the trend of hiring retired Philippine Army members and evaluating whether current qualifications meet the complex demands of custodial work.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly followed ethical principles to ensure the safety, rights, and dignity of all informants, emphasizing informed consent, confidentiality, integrity, beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose and voluntarily signed consent forms, with their identities protected and interviews conducted in safe, comfortable environments. The research avoided any actions that might cause harm or distress, ensured fair and respectful treatment of all custodial personnel, and upheld their right to withdraw or decline to answer questions at any time. Trustworthiness was established through credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability achieved by validating research instruments, systematically collecting and verifying data, providing rich descriptions for future applicability, adhering to established research procedures, and grounding findings in participant accounts. Reflexivity and bracketing were also practiced to minimize researcher bias, with the researcher maintaining a reflective journal and setting aside personal assumptions to ensure that the participants' authentic experiences guided the analysis.

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